

Paper 5**NOVEL STRATEGIES TO COMBAT CHALLENGES IN LOGISTICS POST PANDEMIC - A CASE STUDY****Sagar Srinivas¹ Dawn Prakash²**¹Research Scholar, Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University Mangaluru 575001, India; ORCID: 0000-0002-1662-3769; Email: sagarsrinivas59@gmail.com;²Assistant Professor MBA Department SDM PG Centre for Management Studies & Research Mangaluru, Karnataka, India
Email: dawn.prakash@sdmmba.ac.in**ABSTRACT**

During this pandemic period, there have been many industries & businesses which have been impacted. Transport and Logistics is no different with numerous borders been closed yet the need for essential commodities to be shipped always remained the primary focus with loads of challenges. A ton of business has endured confronting misfortunes with some in any event, being compelled to close down for time being or forever. This has also created a huge challenge for the supply chain and logistics industry too. The current situation is a gigantic test which serves as a chance on the off chance that we think about different necessities of individuals and organizations the whole way across the world. If novel ideas to create an impactful logistical system can be put into place a Win-Win circumstance can truly arise. With the advent and rise of Technology, the scope has further enhanced.

Keywords: Novel Logistics Ideas, Logistics Post Pandemic, Challenges in Logistics Post Pandemic

1. INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus' exceptional impact on the worldwide economy has been detrimental for its synchronous disturbance of both interest and supply. As countries and enterprises restart the economy, reviving stockpile chains is basic need of the hour. Close term issues - The closure of the car business set off by Covid has suddenly stifled incomes, driving numerous providers, particularly the more modest ones, to intense monetary pressure. With restricted stores huge numbers of them may not endure the late spring. Welcoming elective providers on stream at short notification isn't simple. Making new apparatuses and creation frameworks with imperative quality requires significant investment, exertion and consumption — difficult in an economy simply blending from upheld hibernation. Moreover, the lopsided speed of resumption of action across locales and areas brings about vulnerability across all components of the worth chain. Numerous providers rely upon provisional work — frequently transient workers who have experienced impressive difficulty and will set aside some effort to re-visitation of work. Key difficulties - The foreseen downturn and comparing request languor for the close to term will energize scaling back of limit and thusly this is probably going to propel industry combination. Indeed, even before Covid, getting ready for a move towards zap and a bigger part for gadgets, the automobile business had dispatched a whirlwind of acquisitions and consolidations among providers. Presently, providers whose accounts have been attacked will

empower a new flood of acquisitions by generally very much supported adversaries. There will be a major change in the entire system of inventory network after the pandemic, more spotlight will be on examining the vulnerability in future which can assist with keeping the progression of products uninterrupted. There will likewise be need to deal with the workers Organizations have an occasion to reshape their coordination's working model to expand adequacy, proficiency and flexibility.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

(a) Food industry: As indicated by Staniforth,2020; Every industry on the planet hopes to perceive how the COVID-19 flare-up will influence the assembling business, and the food business is the same as different enterprises. Notwithstanding, the distinction in the food business from different enterprises is to deliver items that are fundamental for everyday life. Everyone realizes that on the off chance that one industrial facility shuts, a specific number of individuals who works at these plants can possibly starve, however on the off chance that processors and wholesalers are contaminated, all individuals are in danger. Also, the food business is a significant area with respect to economy. Nonetheless, food area faces various arrangements of difficulties contrasted and different areas that are not basic for every day life, for example, the travel industry and aeronautics during a pandemic.

(b) Supply Chain: As per Devereux et al., 2020; Flynn, 2020; The supply chain influences makers, merchants, and shoppers, yet in addition food-preparing plants that are work concentrated. Creation was diminished, suspended, or briefly ended in numerous plants because of the laborers who were discovered to be COVID-19 positive and who were hesitant to go to work, feeling that they would become ill grinding away, generally in meat-handling food organizations at the hour of the flare-up. Hence, it was believed that the creation limit of pork offices diminished by around 25% in late April.

(c) Logistics System: As per, Li and Haimes, 1992, Li, 1993, Logistics frameworks are mind boggling frameworks. It is anything but difficult to plan it into the arrangement of frameworks (SoS) area. In earlier investigations, for example, the ones evaluated in, the examination regularly doesn't zero in overall framework with the full contemplations of the particular convoluted collaborations. With regards to SoS or enormous scope frameworks when all is said in done, the particular improvement issues generally include different targets in a mind boggling setting. This calls for new examination to look at logistics frameworks from the SoS approach. This is particularly noticeable as COVID-19 is a powerful change which influences one individual from the logistics framework, yet fundamentally all individuals. All things considered, an all-encompassing frameworks approach should be received to determine weighty answers for help. This additionally identifies with strategy producers (e.g., governments) just as worldwide bodies.

(d) Economical Supply Chain: As per Dubey et al. 2017 Chi, Huang, and George 2020; Sustainable Supply Chain (SSC) is the crossing point of supply chain and feasible turn of events. It incorporates monetary, social and climate issues to deal with their associations with providers. In the pandemic circumstance, the associations are moving towards request driven model for dealing with their SCs. The COVID-19 has made extreme tension on the associations to give both center and non-center administrations and subsequently they are changing to new types of SCs. The organizations rethink outsiders and use their SC network joint efforts with multi-level providers to satisfy the interest and supply. The GSCs are using computerized and

non-advanced structures to build up their compass through both the structures for supporting on the lookout. The SCs oversee stock gives admittance to continuous stock data, request estimate and request subtleties to the provider that gives advantages to the upstream provider. The focal point of the SCs is zeroing in on extra organizations, coordinated efforts; esteem expansion, co-creation, enhancement of conveyance and pickup choices, omni-channel supply chains, overseeing unpredictable interest, request satisfaction, embracing advanced applications, and group and asset the board. According to data sharing, examines assign that an association structure of the firm is subject to coordinated effort. The unsure circumstance has implemented the SCs to team up with various accomplices all together for lessening danger and vulnerability. This coordinated effort has upgraded the presentation of the SCs by diminishing a company's expense and improving incomes. The cooperation of retailers and providers helps in dropping the bullwhip impact in SCs. The supply chains take various structures, the partnership of various areas, in unmistakable sizes target remembering enduring of the influenced populace.

2. THE OBJECTIVES AND METHOD

The objectives of the present study is focused on how new ideas can be formulated in logistics post pandemic. In this present study in order to get a basic understanding of challenges in Logistics, the data has been collected from secondary sources along with primary data from observational methods and creative thinking.

3. STRATEGIES TO COMBAT LOGISTICS CHALLENGES

1. **Living Segmentation:** Expanded number of more modest measured client portions to fulfill different prerequisites and altering and refining them powerfully on a "living" premise
2. **Partnerships and Collaborative Platforms:** Dynamic commitment of outer accomplices to give resources and administrations to clients, empowered by computerized stages that associate resources, individuals, cycles and things to expand coordinated effort
3. **Applied Intelligence and Performance Management:** Utilization of examination, "consider the possibility that" situation displaying, nonstop measurements observing and execution improvement wanting to upgrade activities and convey enhanced the client.
4. **Continuous Innovation:** An "probe the-go" way to deal with drive development and increment client esteem for each supply chain with an attention on feasible practices
5. **Communicate adequately:** Guarantee proactive correspondence with on location and telecommuters, providers, transporters and clients. In this season of serious interruption, standard, clear and compelling correspondence across the entire logistics biological system is fundamental.
6. **Support the labour force:** Address the actual wellbeing and mental prosperity of the center labour force just as the all-encompassing logistics labour force.
7. **Technology Usage:** With new technologies like block-chain in huge demand, logistics management will surely benefit and all the stakeholders involved would find the challenges can be converted into smart opportunities post pandemic. Already it is been used in certain sections and is proving to be a real game changer.

4. CONCLUSION

When challenges surfaces, there are always new opportunities too which presents itself. With the rapid change in technologies and invention of new ideas and collaboration which are not restricted to any geographical or political boundaries, challenges created during pandemic in logistics can be converted into opportunities with the right mindset which has to be flexible, robust, technology driven, efficient, collaborative. That is the only way the challenges in logistics can be tipped to magnificent opportunities.

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